

QUIZ**LAST NAME: LAWAL****FIRST NAME: BOLARINDE****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 06****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following statements best describes plagiarism?

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and give credit to the author of that source of information.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.¹**
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information and give credit to the supervisor of that source of information.
- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the library where he found that source of information.

2. There are reasons why a writer must mention the sources he consulted in writing. Which of the following reasons is NOT correct?

- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

- It is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit.
- To make the writing academically sound.**²
- It is a serious academic offence that can have some serious consequences.
3. **What are the three types of questions researchers ask in order for their writings to meet readers' expectations?**
- Concept questions, practical questions, and applied questions.**³
- Concept questions, applied questions, and research questions.
- Concept questions, objective questions, and practical questions.
- Concept questions, practical questions, and feasibility questions.
4. **To generate a research topic and the hypothesis, the researcher must first ask relevant questions that are worth answering; what important steps must the researcher take to ask such fundamental questions?**
- By consulting a mentor and a supervisor
- By consulting various sources such as previous works from areas of interest, for example, internet, print sources, Philosopher's Index, journals, and so on.**⁴
- By developing a scholarly concept note.
- By forming an interest group for interviews.

² Ibid.

³ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8TH ed. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press Chicago and London, 2013), 16–17.

⁴ Ibid., 18–21.

5. Regarding the two citation styles, which of the following statements rightly describes one of the styles? What is the category of this citation style?
- You signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it. This is a note-bibliography citation style.
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it. This is an author-date citation.
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing an alphabet at the end of the sentence in which you refer to it. This is a note-bibliography citation.
 - You signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it. This is an author-date citation.⁵**
6. From among the options below, identify the correct arrangement for the online journal article bibliography:
- Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number (Date of Publication): YY–YY. Accessed Date of Access. URL.⁶**
 - Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. (Date of Publication) "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number: YY–YY. Accessed Date of Access. URL.
 - Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. (Date of Publication) "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number: YY–YY. Accessed Date of Access. URL.

⁵ Ibid., 87–88.

⁶ Ibid., 92.

- Author's First Name, Author's Last Name. "Title of Article: Subtitle of Article." Title of Journal Volume Number, Issue Number: YY–YY. Accessed Date of Access. URL. (Date of Publication).

7. **The following are the key steps for the literature review.**

- Developing a conceptual framework, identifying and retrieving, review and analyse, and synthesising (write and review).
- Identifying and retrieving, developing a conceptual framework, review analyse, and synthesising (write and review).
- Identifying and retrieving, review and analyse, synthesising (write and review), and developing a conceptual framework.**⁷
- Developing conceptual framework, review and analyse, identifying and retrieving, and synthesising (write and review).

8. **The unique features of Zotero citation assistant include:**

- Chrome extension for citing sources online, Microsoft word plug-in for inserting footnotes, referencing, and creating the bibliography.**⁸
- Chrome extension for argumentation, Microsoft word plug-in for inserting footnotes, referencing, and for creating the bibliography.
- Microsoft word plug-in for inserting footnotes, referencing, and creating the bibliography. Also, for publishing.
- Microsoft word plug-in for describing methodologies, referencing, and creating the bibliography. Also, for publishing.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2008), 50–52.

⁸ EUCLID, "Zotero Training 01" (Euclid University, 2020), accessed April 3, 2021, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.

9. *The fox had entered the garden before she could realize that the labourers left the door open. Mr. Brown screamed, “Who is there”?* **The above statement is intended for British readers; identify any errors contained in the statement.**

- No errors are contained in the statement.
- The word ‘realize’ is spelt in American style; ‘Mr.’ should not have a period in front.
- The word ‘realize’ is spelt in American style; the ‘?’ should be inside the quotation mark.
- The word ‘realize’ is spelt in American style; ‘Mr.’ should not have a period in front; the ‘?’ should be inside the quotation mark.⁹**

10. **Why is the methodology chapter critical in the dissertation?**

- Because it is the chapter that tells readers the details of the research sites.
- Because it is the chapter that tells readers why the researcher took a research decision on the topic, and how he/she implemented the decisions.¹⁰**
- Because it is the chapter that tells readers why what has been done on the topic, and what is new.
- Because it is the chapter that tells emphasise to the readers the findings and conclusion of the research.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 29.

¹⁰ Philip Adu, “Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter” (National Centre for Academic and Dissertation Excellence (NCADE), December 28, 2020), accessed March 6, 2021, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. "Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter," National Centre for Academic and Dissertation Excellence (NCADE), December 28, 2020. Accessed March 6, 2021. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-4/>.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2008.

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

EUCLID. "Zotero Training 01," Euclid University, 2020. Accessed April 3, 2021. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-2/>.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8TH ed. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press Chicago and London, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.